

First Evidence of Solar Neutrino Interactions on ^{13}C

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The SNO+ Experiment

Overburden of ~ 6000 m.w.e.

Rope system
Hold-up and down

Acrylic vessel
12 m diameter

Ultra-Pure Water

~ 9300 PMTs

Target Material
LAB scintillator (780 tonnes)

Introduction

Organic scintillator is made up of long carbon chains:

The six chains with the highest proportions in SNO+ LAB

Introduction

The threshold for neutrino interaction on ^{12}C (and H) is above the solar energy spectrum.

The six chains with the highest proportions in SNO+ LAB

Introduction

However, the 1.1% natural abundance of ^{13}C means that we have around 8 tonnes of ^{13}C atoms in the SNO+ detector.

The six chains with the highest proportions in SNO+ LAB

Introduction

^{13}C nuclei can undergo a CC interaction with neutrinos with a threshold of 2.2 MeV.

The six chains with the highest proportions in SNO+ LAB

${}^8\text{B}$ Solar neutrinos produced in the Sun

8B Solar neutrinos produced in the Sun

Arrive at Sudbury, Canada

Reach detector 2 km underground

Interact with ${}^{13}\text{C}$ nuclei

Event Diagram

- Previously unobserved ^8B neutrino charged current interaction.
- We only consider interactions to the ^{13}N ground state.

Cross Section

- The cross section of the interaction is orders of magnitude larger than the electron elastic scattering (ES) process.
- The expected rate of $^{13}\text{C} - \nu_e$ interactions is $R = 21.9_{-2.5}^{+3.4} \text{ ev/yr/kt}$ of LAB

Ref: Theoretical cross section [3]

Prompt Event

Prompt e^- ($E_{\nu_e} - 2.2 \text{ MeV}$)

Prompt Event

- An electron with energy: $E_{\nu_e} - 2.2 \text{ MeV}$
- Imposing a 5 MeV cut removes most background. For example, the ^{208}Tl decay ($Q = 5 \text{ MeV}$).
- The remaining prompt background is ^8B elastic scattering on electrons.

Delayed Event

Prompt e^- ($E_{\nu_e} - 2.2 \text{ MeV}$)

Delayed Event

- A positron annihilation with energy: [1.0 to 2.2] MeV.
- The annihilation produces two gammas, which are detected.
- The increase below 1.2 MeV is due to the β^- -decay of ^{210}Bi .

Correlated Backgrounds

A correlated signal matching the ^{13}C interaction signature would be a background to this measurement.

Natural radioactivity:

- Delayed coincidences from decay chains removed by prompt energy > 5 MeV.

Reactor antineutrinos (IBD):

- Prompt + delayed neutron capture partly overlaps the ^{13}C signal window.
- Short neutron capture time (~ 200 μs) $\rightarrow \Delta T > 0.01$ min cut \Rightarrow negligible contribution.

Remaining Correlated Backgrounds:

- Cosmogenic spallation products
- Atmospheric neutrino interactions (in backup)

Cosmogenic Background

- The highly energetic muons collide with the carbon atoms inside SNO+ producing a range of isotopes.
- Specifically, the muon spallation products, ^{11}Be and ^{11}C , can produce a correlated background signal:

	^{11}Be	^{11}C
Half-life	13.6 s	20.0 min
Decay type	β^-	β^+
Q value (MeV)	11.5	1.98

- Because of SNO+'s depth, the initial rate is low; applying a 60-second cut after each muon further reduces it to 0.0015 ev/yr/kT of LAB.

Analysis Method

The relatively long half-life of the ^{13}N (10 minutes) means the dominant background is from accidental coincidences.

Prompt: ^8B ES on electrons

Delayed: Unrelated radioactive background

~ 10 Minutes

$$\Delta R \leq 1 \text{ m}$$

Analysis Method

- The relatively long half-life of the ^{13}N (10 minutes) means the dominant background is from accidental coincidences.
- A data-driven approach was used to determine the accidental rate.
 - Spurious prompt events produced “fake coincidences” with data events satisfying delayed event cuts.
- The random coincidence rate is determined by the fraction of events resulting in fake coincidences.
 - A Likelihood approach was used, but it was confirmed using a simple cuts-based approach.
 - 230 days of livetime.

PDFs

Using PDFs of the ΔT (0.01 to 60 minutes), ΔR (<1 m) and the delayed energy (1 to 2.2 MeV), the likelihood ratio was constructed.

Likelihood Ratio

Likelihood Ratio

Likelihood Ratio

- 60 events observed, consistent with the expected 63.2 events.
- Distributions are NOT fit; the rates are scaled to the expected.
- Good agreement with the background model.
- Events with a LR > 0 show more consistency with the ^{13}C solar neutrino signal.

Signal Events

Signal Extraction

Measured rate:

$$1.59^{+0.82}_{-0.65} \text{ ev/yr/tonne of } ^{13}\text{C}$$

Consistent with the theory.

The significance is 4.2 sigma.

The error is found using Wilks' theorem.

Cross Section

Converting the observed number into an average cross section:

$$\langle \sigma(E_\nu) \rangle = \left(16.1_{-6.7}^{+8.5}(\text{stat.})_{-2.7}^{+1.6}(\text{syst.}) \right) \times 10^{-43} \text{ cm}^2$$

Ref: Theoretical cross section [3], KARMEN result [7].

Summary

- The SNO+ collaboration reports the first evidence of ^8B solar neutrinos interacting on ^{13}C at a significance level of 4.2 sigma using 230 days of data.
- SNO+'s unique depth makes it an ideal detector to suppress the correlated cosmogenic backgrounds and measure this interaction.
- This is the first measurement of the CC $^{13}\text{C} - \nu_e$ reaction to the ground state of ^{13}N
- Only the second real time measurement of CC interaction of ^8B neutrinos
- The first-time solar neutrinos have been used to measure a cross section

Thank You!

Backup

The SNO+ Collaboration

The SNO+ Experiment

Reactor and Geo Neutrinos

Solar Neutrinos

Neutrinoless Double Beta Decay

Supernova Neutrinos and Exotic

[*] Usman. S, et al. AGM2015: Antineutrino Global Map 2015. Sci Rep 5, 13945 (2015)

^{13}N Ground State

We only consider interactions to the ^{13}N ground state:

- ^{13}N excited states decay via proton emission too rapidly to produce a viable delayed coincidence signal.

Expected Rate

$$R = N_{13C} \Phi \int \sigma(E_\nu) S_\nu(E_\nu) P_{ee}(E_\nu) dE_\nu$$

N_{13C} - Number of ^{13}C atoms

Φ - Solar flux [2]

$\sigma(E_\nu)$ - Cross section [3]

$S_\nu(E_\nu)$ - Normalised ^8B energy spectrum [4]

$P_{ee}(E_\nu)$ - Survival probability (assuming globally fit neutrino oscillation parameters [5])

Expected Rate

Calculating the integral and the error gives:

$$R = 21.9_{-2.5}^{+3.4} \text{ ev/yr/kt of LAB}$$

The dominant systematic error is from the number of ^{13}C atoms, which in turn is from the (very) conservative error on the natural abundance of ^{13}C :

$$\triangleright NA_{13\text{C}} = 1.1_{-0.15}^{+0.05} [6]$$

The conservative error on the cross section is estimated using the variation in different model calculations [3].

Since this result we have measured the ^{13}C abundance in LAB, which will reduce this systematic.

Cosmogenic Background

- Muons produced from cosmic rays
- Most are stopped by the large overburden (6000 m.w.e)
- Leaving a muon rate of ~ 3 per hour
- The highly energetic muons collide with the carbon atoms inside SNO+ producing a range of isotopes.

Cosmogenic Background

- Specifically, the muon spallation products, ^{11}Be and ^{11}C , can produce a correlated background signal:

	^{11}Be	^{11}C
Half-life	13.6 s	20.0 min
Decay type	β^-	β^+
Q value (MeV)	11.5	1.98
SNO+ rate (kt/yr)	1.4 ± 0.3	1111 ± 179

Prompt Background

Delayed Background

NC Atmospheric Background

- Most atmospheric neutrino interactions are too high energy to interfere with this measurement.
- Or they have a short timescale so don't interfere with ΔT window for the ^{13}C signal.
- However, the neutral current (NC) interaction on ^{12}C can produce isotopes which mimic the delayed signal.

NC Atmospheric Background

For example, ^{11}C :

Prompt event:

- Thermalisation of the high-energy neutron

Delayed event:

- Decay of $^{11}\text{C} \rightarrow {}^{11}\text{B} + \nu_e + e^+$ around 20 minute later

This is significantly reduced (< 0.01 ev/yr/kT) by tagging the the neutron when its captured and releases the characteristic 2.2 MeV gamma ray.

^{238}U Decay Chain

Systematics

The MC systematics were largely constrained using coincident $^{214}\text{Bi} - ^{214}\text{Po}$ decays from detector intrinsic background ^{222}Rn levels.

A highly pure sample in data can be selected using:

- The high Q-value of ^{214}Bi β^- decay 3.27 MeV
- The short half-life of ^{214}Po $t_{1/2} = 164 \mu\text{s}$

This data sample was compared with MC to evaluate systematic differences, and the resulting corrections and uncertainties were then propagated to the ^{13}C signal MC.

Giving a total ^{13}C signal efficiency of: $44^{+2.6}_{-1.6}\%$

Data Driven

The number of accidental coincidences is found by:

$$N(\text{Accidental}) = \frac{N(\text{Delayed Cadindates})}{N(\text{Spurious Prompt})} \times N(\text{Data Prompt})$$

- Accidental rate: 0.34 per spurious prompt event
- 173 prompt events found
- Expected background ~59 events

Signal Extraction

The likelihood PDFs can be used to construct a mixed signal and background model, from which the overall relative likelihood can be plotted as a function of signal content.

The expected rate in SNO+ is $R = 7.50_{-2.18}^{+0.98}$ events annually.

It can be expressed as per year per tonne of ^{13}C :

- Within the FV that's 5.67 tonnes of ^{13}C .

Signal Extraction

Measured rate:

$$1.59^{+0.82}_{-0.65} \text{ ev/yr/tonne of } ^{13}\text{C}$$

Calculate the average cross section:

$$\langle \sigma(E_\nu) \rangle = \frac{\text{Measured Rate}}{N_{^{13}\text{C}} \Phi \int S_\nu(E_\nu) P_{ee}(E_\nu) dE_\nu}$$

The error is found using Wilks' theorem.

Multiplicity

The analysis allows for a prompt to have multiple delayed events

- The data-driven approach gives the expected fraction:

Multiplicity	Expected Fraction (%)	Observed Fraction (%)
0	70.45	72.25
1	23.2	20.81
2	5.14	6.94
3	0.96	0.0

Very consistent with the expectation

Note: None of the “signal-like” events has the same prompt.

Event Positions

Uniform distributions throughout the detector.

Signal-like events $LR > 0$

Background-like events $LR < 0$

PDF - Energy

Good agreement between the expected distributions and the data.

Note: This is not a fit. It has been scaled to the expected rate.

PDF - ΔR

Good agreement between the expected distributions and the data.

Note: This is not a fit. It has been scaled to the expected rate.

PDF - ΔT

No evidence for a correlated background for example ^{11}C

Note: This is not a fit. It has been scaled to the expected rate.

KARMEN

- ISIS spallation source of the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in the UK.
- High-energy neutrinos ~ 40 MeV.
- Sensitive to all excited states of the nitrogen as they weren't looking for the delayed coincidence.

$$\langle \sigma(E_\nu) \rangle = \left(50_{-25}^{+25}(\text{stat.}) \text{ }_{-6}^{+4}(\text{syst.}) \right) \times 10^{-42} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ [7]}$$

Cross Section

[7.2 - 15] MeV

[40 - 52] MeV

Cross Section

A range of theoretical cross section models for the ground state interaction

Cross Section

Decay time [1]

$$\sigma(E_\nu) = \frac{2\pi^2 \ln 2}{m_e^5 ft} p_e E_e F(Z, E_e)$$

- $F(Z, E_e)$ is the fermi factor.
- ft –value of the ^{13}N decay is experimentally determined as $\log\left(\frac{ft}{s}\right) = 3.667 \pm 0.001$ [8]

Shell-models [3]

- SFO uses a new shell-model Hamiltonian for p-shell nuclei ([9]) and is used here to calculate the expected rate.
- The new Hamiltonian significantly improves the description of magnetic properties in p-shell nuclei.
- Provides more accurate predictions of magnetic moments and Gamow–Teller transition strengths compared to conventional Hamiltonians such as Cohen-Kurath (CK) Hamiltonian.

^{238}U Decay Chain

^8B Energy Spectrum

Solar ^8B Neutrino Flux and Spectrum

- The flux and spectrum of ^8B electron neutrinos have been precisely constrained by measurements of charged-current (CC), neutral-current (NC), and elastic-scattering (ES) interactions across many solar-neutrino experiments.
- The results are fully consistent with the standard solar model and neutrino oscillations.
- Oscillation parameters are also independently confirmed by terrestrial experiments.
- With the solar electron-neutrino spectrum well established, we can now measure the CC cross section on a new nucleus, ^{13}C , for the first time.

Cuts-Based Analysis

Optimise the log likelihood ratio for the expected observation of $S + B$ under the hypothesis of $\mu = S + B$ vs the null hypothesis of $\mu = B$

Where for given cuts ($FV, \Delta R, \Delta T, E_{e^+}$):

S – Number of signal events

B – Number of background events

Once optimized, use these cuts to find the total background rate and then compare to the observed rate.

Cuts-Based Analysis

- The fiducial volume (FV), delayed energy (E_{e^+}), ΔR and ΔT cuts were jointly optimised

Optimum Cuts
FV < 5.3 m
$\Delta R < 0.36$ m
$0.01 < \Delta T$ (min) < 24
$1.14 < E_{e^+}$ (MeV) < 2.2

Cuts-Based Analysis

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FV < 5.3 m
$\Delta R < 0.36$ m
$0.01 < \Delta T$ (min) < 24
$1.14 < E_{e^+}$ (MeV) < 2.2

- These cuts give an expected background number of 0.467 and a signal of 2.67

Four events were observed

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